

D1.3 Technical progress report 1

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable illustrates the progress in the various areas of the Eureka3D project that has just completed its first six months.

The Eureka3D project addresses the growing need of enabling the digital transformation of the Cultural Heritage (CH) sector. Museums, galleries, libraries, archives and archaeological sites need to review and modernise their internal processes from digital capture to end-user access and re-use. They need to re-train their personnel to cope with the new digital responsibilities and roles; to review their infrastructure capacity, in particular with regard to the ability to process 3D contents; to generate a novel holistic documentation of the digital objects.

The existing services of the Europeana platform is a good starting point to support sharing and re-use, but an integration with more advanced, powerful and safe services is needed to answer to the challenges and demands, particularly keeping in focus the needs and requirements of smaller institutions. In this light, the project is in fact contributing to the development of the common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage, in close collaboration with Europeana Foundation.

To enable all this, the project is actively performing various tasks relating to:

- The creation of a European-based Data Hub with resources and tools accessible by CHIs of any size: such services will also be integrated with the Europeana environment and published on the EOSC European Open Science Cloud, to better support access and research in cultural heritage;
- A capacity building programme to improve the knowledge and digital transformation capacity of professionals in the cultural sector, with specific focus on high-quality 3D digitization and collections management;
- A communication and dissemination programme that, besides promoting the project and its achievements, showcases high quality 3D and 2D collections in Europeana also with publications, editorials, case studies for providers' journey and reuse of digital cultural collections in various areas.

The project is complemented by project management and sound impact assessment activity that supports the design of sustainability routes for the Eureka3D Data Hub, resources and outcomes.

The project is well on track with first outcomes and due deliverables achieved.

The document is composed of the following chapters:

1. Introduction
2. Overview of the progress
3. Details on Work Packages and Activities
4. Conclusions

1. INTRODUCTION

According to the project's Grant Agreement, this document *D1.3 Technical progress report* is the first instance of progress report with detail of the activities, data added or updated, updated risk assessments, the progress towards the project objectives in percentages, highlighting and justifying deviations from the original plan.

In accordance with the provision of the Grant Agreement, the periodic reports are submitted following the templates published on the EU Funding & Tenders Portal. On this basis, the deliverable D1.3 is composed by the content provided on the EC Portal (Part A of the Technical Report) and by this document that contains the narrative parts of the Technical Report (Part B). The Financial Report is not part of D1.3 and is expected to be submitted to EC at the end of the Action.

In particular, this document provides an overview of the progress achieved at Month 6 and the status of execution of the workplan, including details on the progress of each WP and task, and information about achieved milestones and deliverables.

ROLE OF THIS DELIVERABLE IN THE PROJECT

This deliverable summarizes the activities performed in the project towards the expected objectives in the first 6 months of work. Despite the initial stage of the project, various challenges were identified and already addressed, namely: to set-up the communication and dissemination platform and channels, to cover both internal communication among the partners and communication towards the external communities; the importance of establishing a factual dialogue between partners of different backgrounds that need specialist expertise and support; and the early reflections on impact assessment that proved rather complex in order to achieve an effective impact in the various areas and prepare for future exploitation.

This deliverable D1.3 is complemented with the D1.2 Integration Report that describes the planning of the work that will be carried out to integrate the outcomes of the Eureka3D project into the common European data space for cultural heritage.

The deliverables D1.2 and D1.3 are verification means for Milestone 1 that is timely achieved.

2. OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS, BASED ON THE TECHNICAL REPORT TEMPLATE (PART B CHAPTER 1)

Summary of work performed and achievements, results and impacts

Work performed and main achievements

Short summary of progress towards the project objectives. Highlight significant activities and achievements. Provide clear and measurable details.

Analyse the outcome of the project (so far) and its (actual and expected) impact (on target groups, change, innovation etc.), including a description of the European dimension and added value. For the Final Report, include the conclusions of the action.

Report on objectives not fully achieved or not on schedule.

⚠ *Do not simply cut and paste the project summary (filled in online on the Summary for Publication screen). Contrary to the summary, this section is for reporting to the EU and will not be published.*

The project is concluding its first semester with valuable results in the different work packages:

Management and coordination (WP1): the progress monitoring is on track, with regular project and WP meetings to review status and plans for the various tasks; a kick-off meeting in Pisa (23-24 January 2023), monthly telcos and a second project meeting in Roma (6-7 June 2023) were organised with participation of the partners; the due deliverables and milestones were timely submitted. An amendment procedure was agreed with the PO and submitted (pending approval) that includes the addition of new partner imec to support the project progress with multidisciplinary expertise and facilitate partners' joint activities.

3D digitization and capacity building (WP2): the first capacity building event of the project was successfully delivered as an hybrid event on 6/6/2023 in person in Roma (ca. 50 participants) and online (overall ca. 120 participants connected). Support to content providers in accessing and understanding the requirements of the VIGIE Study 2020/654 is provided and work is ongoing. Three online events on capacity building are currently being planned in Autumn 2023, to be realised in collaboration with ICA the International Council on Archives. Various other activities are being planned by the partners to deliver capacity building and training to stakeholders, and an expert group and stakeholder network are currently being formed. Content selection, digitization and metadata preparation activities are started at various paces by the content providers. A service contract for the aggregation task with MINT tool has been established with Datoptron.

Cloud-based services and tools (WP3): The allocation of resources for Eureka3D has started with some hardware dedicated to servers (up to two VMs, 32 vCPUs, 128 GB of RAM and 1 TB of storage) and an S3 Object store with 20 TB of capacity, which is expected to increase during the project according to the project needs. The Deliverable 3.1 "Report on the Eureka3D services and resource hub: design and implementation" has been submitted, which describes the initial architecture of the infrastructure that has been enabled for the project. The identity management system (Check-in) has been configured for the project, which enables authentication and authorisation mechanisms to be used in the project to access the infrastructure resources. Two groups of users have been currently identified to assign permissions: Cloud Operators, who will manage cloud infrastructure, and Content Providers, who will deliver 3D assets to be stored in the infrastructure. New authorisation rules will be added in the project as it progresses. User requirements analysis is progressing with various discussions and a dedicated hands-on session in the project meeting in June, at the moment consulting project partners - but it is planned to extend the discussion to external experts, associate partners and other stakeholders, also possibly including testing exercises with the platform. The data management system, implemented by means of the Data Hub service, has been configured to be used, including the permissions required for the Content Providers of the project. Initial tests on open source libraries for 3D visualisation have started.

Communication, dissemination and impact (WP4): work has started early in the project to provide all necessary communication channels, first of all the project's website, designed according to the chosen visual identity of the project. A blog was already initiated by coordinator Photoconsortium ahead of the project's start date. General information and news about the project is regularly published. The Dissemination and exploitation plan was developed and discussed in the consortium and published as the D4.1. It includes reflections and a planning for the capacity building programme (ref. WP2). Various reflections and discussions about the areas of impact assessment for Eureka3D project started since the beginning of the project, irrespectively of the formal start date (M06) of the task.

3D in Cultural Heritage: <https://www.digitalmeetsculture.net/article/announcing-3d-in-cultural-heritage-event-in-rome/>

Website: <https://eureka3d.eu/>

Project's blog: <https://www.digitalmeetsculture.net/eureka3d-blog/>

OUTCOMES ANALYSIS AND IMPACT ASSESSMENT ON TARGET USERS

Given the project just marked the first 6 months, the initial outcomes are in a very early stage to provide a comprehensive analysis and impact assessment for the various target groups, but it is possible to mention the following:

1 Communication and dissemination - Target: Cultural Heritage Institutions and professionals, technology and service providers, students and researchers, other groups (teachers and cultural educators, other users of cultural data).

The project is rapidly becoming known in the Cultural Heritage community in Europe, due to early communication actions revolving around few key pillars:

- online channels: project website, project blog and social media are constantly kept updated and expanded. Partners are promoting the project via their own channels. A project's newsletter is under development.
- participation in events: the project was presented in the Europeana Aggregators Forum (5-6 April), in the international event in the context of the Swedish EU presidency "Why 3D matters" (18 April), and in the "Shaping the world of 3D workshop (29 June). Additionally a poster with a presentation about the project took place at the EGI annual event in Poznan (19-23 June).
- cooperation agreements: the network of stakeholders is being built by establishing connections with other CHIs,

technology projects and groups of interest. Examples of collaboration initiated or established so far include the INCULTUM project on cultural tourism, Archéoscience CNRS Bordeaux, ICA the International Council on Archives (via the coordinator Photoconsortium), Museovirasto the Finnish Heritage Agency, University of Basel, INSPAI Diputació Girona, GENCAT Cultura (particularly relating to the Giravolt 3D digitization project), meemoo.

- informal and formal relationships with the other DEP-funded projects (AI4Europeana, DE-BIAS, 5DCulture) are ongoing, with the most notable networking session initiated by Photoconsortium and coordinated by Europeana, held online on 24 January 2023 and aiming at identifying common challenges and strategies to support the Europeana Data Space for Cultural Heritage. Additionally, as with the other projects, Eureka3D was invited to take part in the CNECT CEDCHE meeting on 4 July 2023.

2 Data Hub and services - Target: Project partners, CHI professionals, technology and service providers, users of cultural data

The discussions about requirements, functionalities and resources of the Eureka3D cloud-based data hub and tools are progressing intensively with the first outcomes already delivered (cfr. Milestone 8 and D3.1 timely submitted) and a dense programme of dedicated telco with the various partners. In the project meeting in Roma on 6/6/2023, a hands-on session with tutorial for the partners was jointly delivered by responsible partners EGI and AGH Cyfronet ACK.

3 Capacity building and training - Target: Cultural Heritage Institutions and professionals, technology and service providers, students and researchers, other groups (teachers and cultural educators, other users of cultural data)

The capacity building effort of the Eureka3D project is embedded and linked to the overall Europeana capacity building framework, that aims to facilitate and harmonise the development and practice of capacity building programmes of events (in their various phases of organisation, endorsement, evaluation, satisfaction measurements) and other activities both by Europeana, and by professionals throughout the cultural heritage sector.

Three main areas are identified as macro-topics of capacity building and training:

- How to digize 3D in good quality
- Metadata and paradata
- The Eureka3D cloud-based data hub and services

All the Eureka3D partners are involved in the task both as learners and as operators: all partners will in fact deliver capacity building actions such as: online and onsite events; participation in the development of training materials; evaluation of training needs and of expected learning outcomes; impact assessment and quality evaluation of the actions. Training materials and other learning resources produced by the project will be made publicly available in particular via the project's website and in other channels such as the upcoming Europeana Learning Platform. The project manager Valentina Bachi (Photoconsortium) is in fact part of the current Europeana Capacity Building Working Group and will provide the inputs from the point of view of the project in the development of the Europeana new learning environment, that in the near future will also be used to deliver and share Eureka3D training outcomes to a larger community. A specific workshop on capacity building and training took place for Eureka3D partners on 13/6/2023, led by Europeana (Sebastian ter Burg).

4 Editorials - Target: Europeana users and community

An editorial calendar with expected publication dates on Europeana website and Europeana Pro was agreed, as indicated in D4.1. The editorials to be produced by the project are clarified and are in preparation, under coordination of the Communication and Editorial Subgroup. Initial planning for publication is drafted and indicated in the D1.2 Integration Report. Additionally, news items about the project are regularly published in the project's blog and reported via Feed RSS in the project's website.

Implementation plan and efficient use of resources

Implementation plan

Report on changes to the implementation plan (if any).

A request for amendment was submitted in April 2023, principally in order to accommodate a new partner, imec, with a role in supporting and facilitating efficient collaboration between the technical partners and the content providers in the consortium. In this light, imec will participate in tasks WP1 (1 PM) and WP2 (2.6 PM). Also, the role of imec is important in supporting the pilot that the project is running. The pilot includes European CHIs to participate in the experimental use of the 3D digitisation methodologies and workflows provided by CUT, and in accessing and testing the computing and storage services provided by EGI and its affiliate AGH Cyfronet ACK; additionally the pilot includes aggregation services to publish the collections in Europeana.

During the pilot activities, all the necessary technical support for the use of the cloud services is provided to pilots participants by AGH Cyfronet, supported by EGI and in collaboration with partner imec. In particular, imec will facilitate the cooperation providing its trusted multidisciplinary technical expertise, to help harmonise the interests and blend competencies of the various partners - who belong to different sectors, namely: e-infrastructure providers (EGI and AGH), 3D specialists (CUT), CH Institutions (CRDI, Bibracte, Museo della Carta), and partners of the Data Space for CH (the operator Europeana Foundation and the aggregator Photoconsortium).

This change of the implementation plan with the addition of imec does not impact on the successful implementation of the functions foreseen in the role of coordination of Photoconsortium, which instead will take advantage of the new competences that would enter in the project.

In the amendment request, minor changes are also provided, namely:

- A small increase of resources allocated to task 4.4 Impact Assessment in Photoconsortium's budget. This change is needed for the benefit of the task, given that during the first three months of the project we verified how connecting different stakeholders and actors in the light of achieving a durable impact requires more effort than originally estimated;
- An increase of resources in the travel cost budget of Photoconsortium to cover the costs for the reimbursement of travels to associate partners in the project (such as Archéoscience CNRS Bordeaux) and members of the expert group which is currently being formed, to facilitate participation in the project's events
- A shift in the Other costs category for partner Museo della Carta, in order to digitize and aggregate more content than originally foreseen and to realise a video to promote its new participation in Europeana.

The proposal for a new partner addition was discussed and agreed with the PO before launching the amendment procedure. Resources needed by imec are moved from Photoconsortium's budget. Original maximum grant amount as approved does not change.

Besides these changes that are subject of the pending amendment procedure, no other modifications in the implementation plan occur in the reporting period.

Project management, quality assurance and monitoring and evaluation strategy

Report on changes to the overall project management concept, quality assurance and monitoring and evaluation strategy (if any).

The management is coordinated by Photoconsortium in close collaboration with the WP leaders and the other partners, according to the provisions of the Consortium Agreement and expected quality assurance and monitoring processes as described in the Grant Agreement.

The project was launched with a kick-off meeting hosted by the coordinator in Pisa on 23-24 January 2023. In the meeting, overall review of the implementation plan, with a focus on the first 6 months of work, was provided. All WP leaders provided a detailed plan for each task, with allocation of roles and expected activities to be carried out in the next period. Planning for deliverables and milestones was also done with allocation of peer reviewers for each deliverable. Already at the kick-off meeting, the date and location of the first capacity building event of the project was

agreed (Rome, 6th June) to be joined with a plenary meeting (6-7 June, same location).

Monthly project telcos are regularly run with the partners group and topic-specific telcos are also taking place, especially for the activities of WP3 (cloud-based services and tools requirement analysis and development) and for actions of WP4 (dissemination and communication, impact assessment and evaluation). Agenda is circulated before the meeting and notes are shared afterwards.

Tools for internal communication are in place as described in the D1.1 timely submitted on M02.

Cost effectiveness and financial management *(n/a for Lump Sum Grants)*

Inform about significant budget overruns or important changes in the financial management (if any).

Nothing to report in the period.

Critical risks and risk management strategy

Report on the state of play concerning the risks and risk mitigation measures (if any).

No specific issues are reported in the period under examination, as none of the risks occurred and no additional risks are envisaged.

However, following the launch of the project and experiencing the complexity of the various action, the amendment procedure was requested in order to reinforce some areas of the project where risks 1 and 2 could be encountered, in specific:

- different backgrounds, expertise and technical language used by the various partners may impact on the project progress, particularly on the development of the cloud-based services and tools,
- the complexity of 3D digitization, especially in the light of supporting CHIs to fully understand and implement the recommendations of VIGIE Study 2020/654, may require dedicate support to avoid the occurrence of obstacles in the achievement of the expected digitization results.

The support from the new partner imec will be beneficial to these regards.

With regard to the assessment and delivery of impact (risk 7) because of the complexity of the work and to avoid possible further difficulty in the execution of the task, the resources allocated to T4.4 in Photoconsortium's budget have been reinforced.

Consortium cooperation and division of roles (if applicable)

Report on changes in the way the participants work together (Beneficiaries, Affiliated Entities, Associated Partners, etc.).

The consortium cooperation and division of roles is effective and does not present any difficulty among the partners.

An amendment request procedure was launched following the experience in the first months of the project with the main aim to improve the original planning for partners cooperation, by including a new partner (imec) with a specific technical and multidisciplinary expertise that supports partners connection in the pilot. Also some shifts in budget are foreseen in the amendment to reinforce the impact assessment task, which showed already in the early days of the project a complexity and interconnection of dependencies and cross-impacts that was not fully envisaged at the time of proposal preparation. Finally, some resources were moved to travel costs for reimbursement of external experts invited to participate in project's encounters. This proved particularly useful already with the established collaboration with Archèovision CNRS Bordeaux, by enabling one expert to join the project event in Roma on 6-7 June 2023. Expected outcomes of the collaboration relate to the improvement of the cloud-based services and the inclusion of the CNRS 3D viewer tool in the available resources presented in the Eureka3D Data Hub and services. Work to create and expand consulting groups as part of the project's advisory board of experts and the stakeholder network is ongoing.

Project teams and staff

Report and explain deviations from Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement regarding the organisation of staff or project teams. .

No deviations occur from the GA relating to project team and staff.

It is worth to mention the following details:

- WP4 leader CRDI launched a public call for hiring an expert in communication and EU projects' dissemination to fully operate the WP4 activities and coordination. The candidates were examined, and the selected person was introduced in the project starting from May 2023.
- Museo della Carta is involving a PhD student in the project in order to support online publication and metadata creation for the archival materials that will be aggregated in Europeana as part of the project.
- Bibracte assigned a dedicated expert in charge of the communication part, and recruited a specialist archaeologist with advanced skills in digital humanities and thesauri to support content selection, metadata creation and delivery of the files. Additionally, a specialist in 3D modelling is expected to join the team in Summer 2023 to take care of the ceramics and pottery collection's digitization.
- Europeana Foundation involves various persons of the staff on the different tasks, and normally appoints one of them to be the principal connection or reference point of the project. In January, the appointed person was Ilektra Osmani, who resigned from Europeana in March 2023. For this reason, Lianne Heslinga was then appointed as the main reference point for the project.

Consortium management and decision-making (if applicable)

Report on important changes in the management or decision-making mechanisms.

Nothing to report from Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement provisions.

Impact

Impact

Report on changes in your impact analysis/strategy (if any) and the effects on the project/need for adaptations.

Please also describe any innovations or potential innovators emerging from the project with the potential to benefit other activities of the Digital Europe Programme.

Preparation for the Impact Assessment, T4.4 M6-M24, included a detailed workflow diagram of the project, in line with the Europeana Impact Playbook, which identified the key stakeholders and beneficiaries of the EUreka3D project. Impact points have been isolated and partners of the project have been given tasks to ensure that the impacts are taken into account when planning and actioning the various activities going forward. There is no anticipated variation to the Impact strategy but it must be noted that as a large part of the project involves a pilot and capacity building, the measurement of impact within the timeline of the project itself is limited. The major drivers of impact include documentation (guidelines, best practice, and use cases from the pilot) and events (including: training, events, workshops, webinars). Disseminated and actioned within the project, these drivers will prepare stakeholders for capacity building, related to the digitisation of 3D assets, but the tangible results of the impact will not be fully realised by the identified stakeholders until they put these new skills into action.

Therefore, our project impact measurements are refined to the quality of the material we produce within the project, the lessons our internal project partners learn from the infrastructure pilot, the targeted stakeholders we reach during the project and the feedback and dialogue that result from the activities of the project. There is a significant level of

sustainability to preserve and disseminate the project resources that will have an impact beyond the life of Eureka3D but the impacts here can only be estimated by extrapolating the knowledge and capacity building attained during the 2 years of the project.

It is important to mention that this project aims to support the scopes of the European common data space for cultural heritage and more largely in this context to support Cultural Heritage Institutions in their digital transformation journey, with particular regards to 3D digitization, management and sharing. For this reason, the capacity building programme of Eureka3D is particularly important to disseminate and foster adoption of the VIGIE Study 2020/654 recommendations for high quality 3D content and metadata-paradata creation; also, CHIs benefit from learning about successful experiences of other CHIs who share the same challenges; finally, it will be necessary to raise awareness of the Eureka3D cloud-based Data Hub and tools to enable CHIs outside the consortium to access and use these resources. Assessing the outcomes of the capacity building and training programme of Eureka3D is a key part of impact assessment.

As mentioned, the first event was organised by coordinator Photoconsortium in Roma and online on 6/6/2023, and was a success with ca. 50 participants in the room and over 120 connected online. The post-event survey reported that 100% of respondents agree the event was useful in their work or for personal knowledge.

Few comments collected from the audience:

- *The exhibition of practical cases are always useful to understand the use of 3D digitization in various fields.*
- *The most useful part of the webinar were technicalities behind 3D imaging and would love to hear more about technical part of photogrammetry.*
- *I 100% agree with Valentina about the European Viewer Platform and I would like learn more about archives, storage and digital preservation. Thank you for everything, it was a great event.*

This result is very encouraging and testifies the interest of the CH community and the need to discuss in depth these topics and learn more about challenges and solutions.

In addition to assessing the users satisfaction, a step forward will be to establish mechanisms to assess the learning outcomes of the various actions. Discussion is ongoing together with Europeana to clearly map the intended learning outcomes of the various actions and to develop forms of measurement of participants' learning, in line with the Taxonomy of Educational Objectives by B. Bloom. Examples of measurement mechanisms include quizzes, questions, or specific exercises to be taken by participants, that permit to assess what they can remember, understand, apply etc. from the Eureka3D learning action. Work is ongoing in this direction.

Communication, dissemination and visibility of funding

Report on the communication and dissemination activities undertaken (to whom, which format, how many, etc.) as foreseen in your Dissemination and communication plan. Please inform and justify any changes regarding dissemination and exploitation in comparison with the initial plan.

Describe how the visibility of EU funding was ensured.

If you described your project on your website(s) and/or social media accounts, please provide the links.

During the first six months, the necessary channels and tools have been activated for the execution of the project's initial communication and dissemination plan. It is worth to mention the project's website and the project's blog, that are the key tools for web presence, also showcased in the previous section. Regular updates with publication of news and information is performed jointly by Photoconsortium and CRDI, while the other partners are invited to share information and collaborate to communication and dissemination, especially on social media. The internal communication tools agreed and published in report D1.1 are now being implemented and the workflows are working properly.

At the plenary meeting in Rome at the beginning of June, the bases of the communication and dissemination planning were discussed and approved. Already before the approval of this plan, several necessary communication actions have been carried out, such as the publication and constant updating of the web page, the publication of articles related to the project on the blog, the start of the activity on social media and the promotion of project events and other external events via the existing channels and dissemination by e-mail.

The main communication actions of the first period of the project have focused on disseminating the priority activities of the project, such as the first conference open to the public "3D in Cultural Heritage", in the framework of the Capacity

Building Programme. The main target groups for this first conference were Cultural Heritage Institutions professionals, researchers in 3D for cultural heritage, students, educators and other cultural professionals.

The Eureka3D project has also taken part in an external event, EGI 2023 Conference, to present the project's Data Hub among international scientific communities, computing service providers, European project managers and policy makers. As part of these activities, some printed materials have been produced: a reusable roll-up, an informational flyer about the project or an explanatory poster and brochure about the Data Hub that were exhibited at the EGI Conference.

In terms of internal communication, it has also been agreed to work with the "Communication and Editorial Subgroup", with a representative of each partner, in order to speed up communication between members and optimise resources. The editorial plan has been developed in the context of the communication and dissemination plan. It includes Europeana blogs (4) to show the collections from content providers; Europeana Pro (3) to publish articles on high quality 3D digitisation, capacity building and new services and tools; Europeana galleries (10) created by content providers to showcase aggregated 3D digitised content and some other galleries combining existing content from Europeana and new 3D digitised content within the project framework.

The editorial publications will be spread out throughout the lifetime of the project to maximize engagement and participation.

Sustainability, long-term impact and continuation

Report on changes in your sustainability analysis/strategy (if any).

For the Final Report, describe the follow-up of the project after the end of the EU grant. How will the results be used or further developed. Describe the strategy to ensure sustainability of results and long-term impact. Comment on possible synergies/complementarities with other (EU funded) activities (if any).

Discussions about the integration of Eureka3D outcomes with Europeana and the European Data Space for Cultural Heritage have started, with particular attention to the long term availability of the services and tools under development in the Data Hub (WP3). A business model will need to be carefully shaped in order to grant the continuation and expansion of the services. In particular, costs for storage will need to be assessed and covering mechanisms that are independent from EU funding will need to be planned, keeping in focus the needs and requirements of stakeholder communities, especially those of the smaller CHIs with limited capacity.

Other resources created by Eureka3D such as the training and capacity building materials, outcomes of the events, collections and editorials published in Europeana, website and blog's publications will be maintained beyond the end of the funding period by the commitment of the respective responsible partners.

As a part of the continuation strategy for the Eureka3D concept, participation in the current ECCCH call is foreseen.

Follow-up to EU recommendations

Follow-up to EU recommendations

Highlight corrective actions taken as a result of EU monitoring activities (including follow-up to EU project reviews, if any). List each recommendation/comment and explain how they have been followed up.

Not applicable

3. WORK PACKAGES, ACTIVITIES, RESOURCES AND TIMING, BASED ON THE TECHNICAL REPORT TEMPLATE (PART B CHAPTER 2)

Work Package 1: Project management and coordination			
Activities			
Report on the implementation status of the activities that were to be implemented during the reporting period and explain <u>deviations</u> from Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement. In case an activity was not implemented or a deliverable not produced, please explain why.			
Task No (continuous numbering linked to WP)	Task Name	Implemented? (Yes/No/Partially)	Justification (explain what was done and by whom; explain what was not done and why not; indicate how you intend to handle the situation and new timing; indicate if it was a one-off issue or how you intend to avoid similar issues in the future)
T1.1	Project management	YES, on going	Kick-off meeting was organized in Pisa on 23-24 January 2023. Regular progress monitoring happens via telcos and dedicated meetings. A plenary was organized in Roma on 6-7 June 2023. The internal communication platforms are up and running and in use by the consortium. Reporting guidelines are provided. A progress meeting took place with the PO on 26/6/2023. The D1.3 is timely delivered.
T1.2	Quality control and Data Management	YES, on going	Activities relating to quality criteria of actions and project monitoring with alignment of WP and task progress are regularly performed. GDPR compliance and data management provisions are provided in the D1.1. A disclaimer and privacy policy information is provided in the project's website: https://eureka3d.eu/privacy-policy/
T1.3	Reporting on integration with Europeana CSP operator	YES, on going	Discussions about technical and procedural integration of the project's services and outcomes in the Europeana environment and in the common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage have started since the very beginning. The D1.2 is timely delivered.
Other issues <i>Mention and explain unexpected events and adjustments that had to be made. Explain impact on other tasks, available resources and planning/timing.</i>		<p>A request for amendment was submitted with the scope of including a new partner (imec) in the consortium. If approved, the inclusion of imec would have a valuable impact bringing many benefits in the collaboration between partners of different backgrounds, especially regarding the piloting action that engages content providers with high quality 3D digitization, metadata creation, and development of the Data Hub structure, functionalities and tools.</p> <p>The WP is on track, and it is possible to estimate a progress of 25% against its completion.</p>	

Milestones and deliverables (outputs/outcomes)
<p>The following deliverables and milestones are timely delivered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - D1.1 Internal communication platform - D1.2 Integration report 1 - D1.3 Technical progress report 1 - MS1 First technical and integration reporting

Work Package 2: Capacity building for CH digital transformation and 3D digitisation			
Activities			
<p><i>Report on the implementation status of the activities that were to be implemented during the reporting period and explain <u>deviations</u> from Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement. In case an activity was not implemented or a deliverable not produced, please explain why.</i></p>			
Task No (continuous numbering linked to WP)	Task Name	Implemented? (Yes/No/Partially)	Justification (explain what was done and by whom; explain what was not done and why not; indicate how you intend to handle the situation and new timing; indicate if it was a one-off issue or how you intend to avoid similar issues in the future)
T2.1	Pilot with content providers	YES, on going	Work has already started with content selection and planning of 3D digitization actions, with different levels of readiness for the various content providers. Guidelines are provided and discussed about metadata preparation and/or improvement. Partner CRDI has selected the subcontractor who will perform 3D digitization of the selected collection Partner Bibracte is completing content selection and is planning to start digitization in the summer. Partner CUT has started the digitization workflow of the selected objects. Museum of Paper is currently preparing metadata of the already digitized collections, for which mapping tests are initiated in MINT, and has started discussions for 2D and 3D digitization.
T2.2	Training and capacity building	YES, on going	In close collaboration with Europeana and following the protocols and standards of the Europeana Capacity Building Framework (ECBF), a programme of online and onsite events is being developed. The first event was delivered on 6/6/2023 in Roma, with good

			participation on site and online and positive feedbacks. A dedicated Europeana Training Development workshop was organized with partners on 13/6/2023. Training resources will also be created and published on project's website. More details are provided in the D4.1.
T2.3	Aggregation in Europeana	YES, on going	Support is provided to familiarize content partners with the EPF and EDM. Work has started to analyze the metadata schema of content providers in sight of testing in MINT. A service contract was established by Partner Photoconsortium with DATOPTRON to provide support to MINT mapping and EDM compliance.
Other issues <i>Mention and explain unexpected events and adjustments that had to be made. Explain impact on other tasks, available resources and planning/timing.</i>		The WP and T2.2 in particular are aligned with the capacity building effort currently ongoing in the common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage. In particular, it is expected to integrate the training resources and outcomes of the project in the future Europeana Learning Platform that is currently under development. The WP is on track, and it is possible to estimate a progress of 25% against its completion.	
Milestones and deliverables (outputs/outcomes)			
No deliverables and milestones due in this reporting period.			

Work Package 3: Digital infrastructure and integration of services and tools			
Activities <i>Report on the implementation status of the activities that were to be implemented during the reporting period and explain <u>deviations</u> from Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement. In case an activity was not implemented or a deliverable not produced, please explain why.</i>			
Task No (continuous numbering linked to WP)	Task Name	Implemented? (Yes/No/Partially)	Justification (explain what was done and by whom; explain what was not done and why not; indicate how you intend to handle the situation and new timing; indicate if it was a one-off issue or how you intend to avoid similar issues in the future)
T3.1	Analysis of technical requirements	YES, on going	Work is ongoing with a series of dedicated discussions with consortium partners. It is expected to extend the conversation and requirements collection/analysis also to external stakeholders and experts.
T3.2	Cloud Provisioning of the	YES, on going	The resources are allocated and testing is ongoing. MS8 and D3.1 are timely delivered.

	EUreka3D services and resource hub		
T3.3	Set-up the authentication and authorization infrastructure for the project	YES, on going	The AAI services are operational. A dedicated session of the plenary meeting in Roma on 6/6/2023 was organized as hand-on demonstration and training to partners to enable them to test the Data Hub mechanisms and initial services.
T3.4	On-boarding of the EUreka3D service in EOSC	YES, on going	No specific activities were foreseen for this task in the reporting period, but some discussions and dissemination took place about the EOSC as a resource to support research in cultural heritage and about the importance of an open access approach in sharing cultural collections online.
T3.5	Interoperability with Europeana CSP	YES, on going	Discussions have started with the Europeana technical team and integration plans are reported in D1.2 Integration report.
Other issues <i>Mention and explain unexpected events and adjustments that had to be made. Explain impact on other tasks, available resources and planning/timing.</i>		<p>Despite not foreseen as a deliverable in the project, the technical requirements for the services and tools of the EUreka3D environment will be published on the project website as an outcome from T3.1.</p> <p>The design and the technical implementation of the EUreka3D service and resource hub will be refined iteratively during the next ~18 months, through interviews and interactive sessions organised within the project consortium, and with the broader landscape of 3D cultural heritage preservation institutes.</p> <p>The WP is on track, and it is possible to estimate a progress of 25% against its completion.</p>	
Milestones and deliverables (outputs/outcomes)			
<p>The following deliverables and milestones are timely delivered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - D3.1 Report on the EUreka3D services and resource hub: design and implementation - MS8 The EUreka3D infrastructure is operational 			

Work Package 4: Communication, dissemination and impact assessment			
Activities			
Report on the implementation status of the activities that were to be implemented during the reporting period and explain <u>deviations</u> from Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement. In case an activity was not implemented or a deliverable not produced, please explain why.			
Task No (continuous numbering linked to WP)	Task Name	Implemented? (Yes/No/Partially)	Justification (explain what was done and by whom; explain what was not done and why not; indicate how you intend to handle the situation and new timing; indicate if it was a one-off issue or how you intend to avoid similar issues in the future)
T4.1	Dissemination and exploitation plan	YES	A Plan for communication, dissemination and exploitation, including a marketing plan to support the delivery of the Capacity Building programme, was discussed and agreed among partners, and timely published as D4.1. This plan is an open document which will guide any future development of communication, dissemination and exploitation actions. Task 4.1 is linked with task T4.4
T4.2	Editorials and publications	YES	The project's Communication and Editorial board has been set and regularly meets. A tentative calendar for the Europeana editorials has been agreed with the Europeana team and included in D4.1. News and information are regularly published in the project's blog.
T4.3	Final booklet and final conference of EUreka3D	YES	Talks about the final conference are initiated in the light of choosing the best timing. Towards the end of 2024 in facts there are other events that the project plans to participate, such as the Euromed (normally end of October-early November) I&R (normally mid-November), and the Europeana Annual General Assembly (normally in November). The final conference in Girona should not overlap with these events, and of course should not be organized too close to the Christmas period. Thus, it is expected to be end November – early December. The final booklet will collect all the stories and knowledge generated by the project highlighting the providers' journey in the piloting action. Gathering of the information has started.
T4.4	Impact assessment	YES	Reflections on impact started earlier in the project, since the very beginning. In the Roma plenary meeting on M06, the various areas of impact expected in the project, their interdependencies and the partners' roles were presented and summarized in an impact visual chart. Task 4.4 is linked with task T4.1

<p>Other issues</p> <p><i>Mention and explain unexpected events and adjustments that had to be made. Explain impact on other tasks, available resources and planning/timing.</i></p>	<p>Cooperation agreements are currently being established with a variety of stakeholders involved with 3D digitization of cultural heritage. These stakeholders agree not only to follow the project progress and participate in the capacity building programme, but also to provide their expertise and inputs and to collaborate in creating a valuable library of resources accessible in the project website, where a dedicated page on Resources is already published with initial materials.</p> <p>The WP is on track, and it is possible to estimate a progress of 25% against its completion.</p>
<p>Milestones and deliverables (outputs/outcomes)</p>	
<p>The following deliverables and milestones are timely delivered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - D4.1 Dissemination and exploitation plan - MS10 Communication programme 	
<p>Budget implementation — Use of resources (deviations) <i>(n/a for Lump Sum Grants) (n/a for Additional Pre-financing Report)</i></p> <p><i>Explain <u>deviations</u> from the budget planning (i.e. differences between actual and planned use of resources, especially for personnel). Include explanations on transfers of cost categories in the estimated budget (if applicable)</i></p> <p><i>/If needed, add explanations linked to the report on the use of resources filled in online. Ensure consistency with that report.</i></p>	
<p>The request for amendment includes budget transfer from Photoconsortium to imec to accommodate their participation in the project, and other minor budget shifts as extensively described in the section above (Implementation plan and efficient use of resources) and in the Amendment Request submitted to EC.</p>	
<p>Other issues</p>	<p>Nothing to report in the period</p>

Timetable

No changes from the Grant Agreement.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This document illustrates the progress of EUreka3D project in its first 6 months. It constitute the Part B of the Technical Report. The Technical Report refers also to the information provided in the EC Portal, which constitutes the Part A of the report.

D1.3 Technical Report is complemented by D1.2 Integration Report. This first release of the two reports is timely delivered on M06.

The project is on track with excellent collaboration among partners and all activities initiated, with the first outcomes delivered as planned.

No risks materialized and no deviation is expected.

Efforts to raise awareness of the project and of its capacity building programme are ongoing, and a stakeholders' network is growing.

The impact of the project is being tracked, particularly for the capacity building actions.

An amendment procedure was opened to include imec, a multidisciplinary partner who will bring a great expected benefit to the project.